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The Hidden Danger in Digital Children Games: Gambling

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Abstract

The history of gambling is linked and proportionate to the history of humanity. No matter how far you go back in human history, remnants show that gambling groups have come together, and gambling games are taking place. In digital children games, gambling will and albeit somehow, by paying different costs. Because technology has become an integral part of our lives and the age of using technology has dropped until the preschool age. This may raise concern in terms of gambling, although not for every digital game. With this article, the reason for the danger in digital children's games, the proportion of existing digital games with computer addiction, not by directly targeting the names and brands, was investigated. Because the danger of gambling can occur in any game, in any way, and at unexpected costs. To get to the root of the problem, it was investigated why people spend time at the computer and why they want to earn. However, as the theories revealing the causes of digital children's games also show, gamers are unaware of the gambling danger of many games. When a desire for addiction is combined with the person's urge to show up, the face of invisible danger, gambling appears. With this research, the obvious danger of technology and internet addiction has been taken into consideration as well as gambling, which is a hidden danger. In addition to the devotion of individuals to digital games, their time spent in front of the computer and in unhealthy environments were also examined. Results were tried to be reached in line with the findings obtained.

Keywords: Children games, gambling, gaming, digital games, child abuse.

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Dijital Çocuk Oyunlarındaki Gizli Tehlike: Kumar

Öz

Kumarın tarihi insanlığın tarihiyle bağlantılı ve orantılıdır. İnsanlık tarihinde ne kadar geriye gidilirse gidilsin, kumar gruplarının bir araya geldiğini ve kumar oyunlarının gerçekleştiğini gösteren kalıntılar vardır. Dijital çocuk oyunlarında kumar, bir şekilde farklı bedeller ödenerek de olsa oynanmakta ve oynanacaktır. Çünkü teknoloji, hayatımızın ayrılmaz bir parçası haline gelmiş ve teknolojiyi kullanma yaşı okul öncesi döneme kadar düşmüştür. Bu durum, her dijital oyun için olmasa da kumar açısından endişeyi artırmaya neden olabilir. Bu makale ile dijital çocuk oyunlarındaki tehlikenin sebebi, mevcut dijital oyunların isim ve markaları doğrudan hedef alınarak değil, bilgisayar bağımlılığıyla olan orantısı açısından araştırılmıştır. Çünkü kumar tehlikesi, herhangi bir oyunda, herhangi şekilde ve umulmadık bedellerle karşımıza çıkabilir. Sorunun kökenine inebilmek adına, insanların neden bilgisayar başında zaman geçirdiği ve neden bu oyunlarda kazanmak istedikleri araştırılmıştır. Dijital çocuk oyunlarının oynanma sebeplerini ortaya koyan teoriler de oyuncuların, birçok oyunun kumar tehlikesinden habersiz olduğunu göstermektedir. Bağımlılığın verdiği istek, kişinin kendini gösterme dürtüsü ile birleşince adeta görülmeyen bir tehlike olan kumarın bağımlılık yapan yüzü ortaya çıkmaktadır. Bu araştırma ile gizli bir tehlike olan kumar kadar açıkça gelen teknoloji ve internet bağımlılığı tehlikesi de dikkate alınmıştır. Bireylerin dijital oyunlara bağımlılıkları yanında kapalı ve hatta çoğu zaman sağlıksız ortamlarda bilgisayar başında zaman geçirmeleri de irdelenmiştir. Elde edilen bulgular doğrultusunda sonuçlara ulaşılmaya çalışılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Kumar, oyun, dijital oyun, video oyun

Introduction

No matter what environment, and in which generations the game, is played it is an important activity in the child's development process. Huizinga does not see this activity merely as entertainment, assuming it serves a non-game purpose. Because while children complete the learning process with games, they also improve their physical development, reflex controls and mental health with the game they play (Erdal, 2019:53). However, every game played creates a habit effect as well as a development effect. The fact that children's games played in the digital environment prioritize competitive and leadership qualities reminds us of the theory of uses and gratifications. In other words, the player is the best skill and the fastest responder, and he wants to prove this to other players. "win." The ambition to win deviating from the goal of the game and turning into a winning opportunity can cause players to pay the price. The new situation, which occurs with the dependence of the regardless of the species, and type, is gambling. If the negative aspects of digital technology are ignored (Yurdakul et al, 2013:886), now the game is adapted to the current state of McArdle; It could be a "troublemaker" (Onur & Güney, 2004:7-8). Because spiritually, the child will be dependent on the game, which turns into a substance to satisfy/eliminating its needs (yesilay.org: 2020, E.T. 22.04.2020) due to its emotional or personality structure.

The game is above all an optional, voluntary action (And, 2012:27-8). In many street games that go digital as well as digital games playing with the principle of volunteering on the screen in a

closed room, “there is a loss of self-control and the situation is out of the control of the individual” (Boyacı, 2019:778). Although the negative aspects of digital children's games are discussed more, there are also positive and positive aspects that contribute to the personal development of children. However, children have a dream world and a way of understanding the world (Gökşen, 2014:534, Karademir ve Filiz: 2019:242). They can mix their own world with the real world. The fact that children's world is based on games and entertainment requires that they need a partner for most games and that they have unconditional trust and loyalty to the other party. The way they interpret the world is about goodness, solidarity, friendship, and trust. It can be easy they manipulate, shape, or deceive them. They may not be aware of the dangers of what they do or play, as long as they make them happy. However, like many things that make it happy when it is done, digital games can cause the danger to go unnoticed and turn into gambling regardless of age.

Popular Culture, Digital Games

The 2000s are known as the years when the visual and audio qualities we used in addition to the verbal within the visual possibilities of the digital world where the technology developed (Artu Mutlugün and Topuz, 2020:38-9). As in every field, with the transfer of children's games to the virtual environment, children have created the opportunity to play unfamiliar players in closed environments. Because the digital game has created its own world with realistic graphic drawings, effects and high sound quality. This new and easy-to-access world can take some form of addiction by taking control of the user's self with its interactive interface. However, from a conventional perspective, digital games can generate complex responses. It can be said that it creates a kind of gambling habit with its material payment strategy, especially for many of the digital games that are rapidly becoming popular among young people.

Many parents are disturbed by the violent themes of digital games, while others complain about the time teens spend on playing (Garris, Ahlers and Driskell, 2002:443). While this contradictory situation is the subject of controversy about the effects of digital games on the child, parental control, can push a defense such as not leaving the child's game choice. The question here is whether the subject of the discussion is as much a blessing or a curse as the computer itself. Another question is why people, including adults, want to spend so much time on the computer. Zagalo answers this question clearly: interaction (Zagalo, 2019:87). Multimedia; It became more attractive with the integration of three primary modalities, such as moving images, text, and sound, through a computer. The interaction of the individual with each multimedia modality affects the decision of where to spend time.

Method And Ethical Responsibility

In the creation of this study, the information gathered by the qualitative research method interpreted with a realistic and holistic approach in the natural environment. In the research, the names of the writers and researchers whose knowledge we use are included. For this reason, the international standards (Ethics Principles set by the Editorial Ethics Committee (COPE) <https://publicationethics.org>) were complied with within the research, and the ethical committee report was not required due to the content of the subject.

Theories

Gambling, whose main expectation is to derive more value than invested, is a typical behavior all over the World (Arcan ve Karanci, 2014:251). Although the gambling environment and purpose are different, it is known that gambling is played to win. The magnitude of the risk taken to win can turn an innocent game into gambling. However, starting the game may not mean that a risk will occur even

if it sometimes requires payment. Instead, it can turn into instructive actions, guiding, or developing the ability to make quick and accurate decisions. It can be said that multimedia environments become more attractive day by day, increasing the number of users and bringing dangers. The trend to exclude it entirely by ignoring the tutor's side may bring more significant problems. Four critical theories can explain the reasons for playing digital games and the possibility of turning into gambling addiction.

1. Flow Theory,
2. Self Determination (SDT) Theory,
3. Uses and Gratifications (U&G) Theory,
4. Technology Acceptance Model.

Flow Theory:

A. Boyle et al. (Boyle, E.A, Connolly, Hainey & Boyle, J.M., 2012:772) explain the reasons for playing digital games with theories developed on motivation, communication, and media. In general, they united in the opinion that they dealt with two critical issues and highlighted the participant's subjective experience and motivation. Csikszentmihalyi reminded us that digital interaction, especially the connection with subjective experience and the most effective structure used to explain this connection, is the flow theory. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi (1990:3), who developed the theory of flow, describes the stream as a complex structure with eight different components. The center of the flow is based on the principle of the optimal match between the individual's skills and difficulties. Kişi, bu aşamada zevk almaktadır. One should enjoy it at this stage. Because it is characteristic of the feeling of pleasure, innovation, or winning, and it has eight main components:

- 1) It should be reasonable,
- 2) They should have clear goals,
- 3) Give instant feedback,
- 4) He must have high motivation,
- 5) It can be controlled,
- 6) There must be an award,
- 7) It must be gripping,
- 8) Make the concept of time forget.

In John L. Sharry (2004: 328–347), he is one of the players who explains the interaction that players experience while playing games with the flow theory. Digital interaction, as demonstrated by flow theory components, carries addiction and, ultimately, a risk of turning into gambling. However, there are other theories that can explain how digital games turn into gambling.

Self Determination (SD) Theory:

Edward Deci and Richard Ryan developed it as a motivation and personality theory that focuses on the inner processes behind the organization of personality development and behavior (Wikipedia, 2018: E.T. 13.05.2020). Self-determination theory is an inclusive theory that explains the motivations and reasons of people both in terms of being proactive and in the regulation of passive and alienated behavior within social life conditions. It is solution-oriented, assuming that it takes place through motivation mechanisms. SDT is an approach to human motivation and personality using traditional empirical methods when using an organism metatheory that emphasizes the importance of people's

evolving internal resources for personality development and behavioral self-regulation (Ryan, Deci, 2000: 68). It is the investigation of congenital growth trends and fundamental psychological needs as well as the conditions that encourage these positive processes, which are the basis of people's motivations and personality integrations. Ryan and Deci talk about three essential findings in the experimental method:

1) Proficiency

Harter made White's competence motivation model more understandable, with particular emphasis on developmental effects (Harter, 1978:42-4), and needed to isolate the components of effectiveness motivation at different levels of development. In this regard, examining the effects of failure and success, the relationship between task difficulty and the degree of pleasure experienced, the role of social intermediaries and the environment, personal reward system, internal and external motivation, and competence control have developed person motivational effect correlations.

2) Relationship

It is a theory that describes the need to establish, and healthy maintain interpersonal relationships. Previously, John Donne conducted this research in 1975 with the keyword "No (person) is not an island" (Baumeister & Leary, 1995:497). The relationship is a motivational attachment arising from the need for inevitable interactions. By the belonging hypothesis, people create social loyalties under most conditions and resist the dissolution of existing bonds (Baumeister & Leary, 1995:498).

3. Autonomy

Autonomy is a useful calculation of human motivation in which general needs are determined (Ryan & Deci, 2000:68). SDT, based entirely on human behavior research, tells the tendency to choose activities freely with the principle of "autonomy." Self-determination theory has been applied to many different social behaviors and can potentially explain participation in digital entertainment games.

Uses And Gratifications (U&G) Theory:

Schramm, Lyle, and Parker (Boyle et al, 2012:771) describe this theory in his research titled "Television in The Lives Of Our Children," published in 1961. He argues that entertainment is a particular need for people. To meet these needs, they define a range of media as a need-based motivation. The paradigm's working philosophy is understandably summarized by Schramm, Lyle and Parker: "We have to move away from the unrealistic concept of what television does to children and change the concept of what children do with television"(Lucas, Sherry, 2004:502). The U&G theory has been expanded to explain why children are playing computer with the spread of the network. Accordingly, six critical reasons why people play computers have been removed:

- 1. Arousal:** The biggest reason for playing video is high-quality graphic visuals, sound, and excitement.
- 2. Challenge:** Overcoming challenges draws players. It can be said that some players have the ambition to move to the next level. Because they can trust and respect themselves.
- 3. Competition:** It is mostly the reason for male players. So they can see themselves stronger. They can even make money. The player can be a leader and sought-after person.
- 4. Orientation:** Video games are often played to relieve stress. However, personal reasons, such as spending time, relaxing, and being happy, can be said.
- 5. Fantasy:** Players can be the heroes of their dreams when playing video games. They can do things they wouldn't usually be able to. They can set up fantasy, live in a dream world.

- 6. Social Interaction:** It is the main reason for many individuals to play video games. It is important to be cool and attract attention. Many use video games to interact with their friends and learn about the personalities of others (Sherry, Lucas, Greenberg, Lachlan, 2003:218-9).

Technology Acceptance Model Theory:

Another theory about explaining why people play games is the technology acceptance model (Davis, 1989:335). This theory was developed to explain the determinants of technology acceptance in business and education. The theory proposes the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use as two main factors in this regard. While the ease of use of a system is a contributing factor in explaining participation in entertainment games, perceived usefulness may be less critical in determining the acceptance of games for entertainment purposes.

Discussion

It can be seen that the virtual addiction that we met with television and video games turned into a gambling hazard with the development of technology, secure and faster access. Even though the dimensions of the danger are not the same, their manifestation in every period is a sign of an unavoidable, more significant threat for the coming years. Theories of addiction show that even very innocent behavior can lead to uncontrollable results. This threat will grow further as long as the individual has the desire to prove himself or earn more in every environment.

Communication scientists and sociologists generally gather the reasons for living things to communicate under three items: (Erdal, 2015:46-7).

1. Social reasons,
2. Cultural reasons,
3. Personal reasons.

The essence of all three items is "to exist" and "self-proofing." The basis of social peace and social life comes from here. Interestingly, the "existence" and "self-proof" ego underpins the gambling threat posed by their digital games. These two cases, which are in the genetics of human beings, can be seen as long as an environment like a virus is available regardless of the individual's age, gender, and education level. Erdoğan (2019:881) determines that starting gambling is in adolescence and indicates that starting gambling at a young age in the literature is a significant risk factor for developing gambling problems. In this sense, defending gambling as "pleasure" and "innocent" puts the fact that behaviors with more severe consequences are part of our lives. Learning to live with it, the hidden danger in computer games can prevent some of the harm of gambling. Destruction or believing that it can be destroyed can be a waste of time. Technology, an anthropogenic factor, will not destroy its creator, but its threatening attitude will always continue. Considering that humanity's share in all living beings as biomass is only 0.01% (Bar-On et al., 2018:6509), the effect of the harm done is significant, although the size is large.

Result

Man entered the process of agriculture and building civilizations about ten thousand years ago with settled life. Considering the side effect of culture, the history of gambling is almost the same as that of man. It is known that some types of bets have been made since the beginning of human history. But today, gambling with digital games stands as a great danger, especially in the world of children. It is of great urgency and importance to take severe measures against this growing danger.

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